
Best Practice Guide - Cray XE (V3.1)

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1. Introduction

This best-practice guide is designed to help users get the best productivity out of the PRACE Cray XE (and to a lesser extent XT) systems. We will cover a wide range of topics including:

- Architecture
- Code porting and compilation
- Debugging tools
- Serial optimisation and compiler flags
- Parallel optimisation
- I/O best-practice and optimisation
- Performance analysis tools

We will focus on providing information that is generally applicable to all Cray XE systems but some information is provided separately for the site-specific reason. We will also provide links to site-specific information in the relevant places.

1.1 PRACE Cray XE/XT Systems

Cray XE systems are hosted by a number of PRACE partner sites including:

Tier-0 - Hermit, HLRS, Germany Hermit is a new PRACE Tier-0 system located at HLRS, Germany. This system will be installed in 3 steps and currently the system is in Installation Step 1; the final step: Installation Step 2 is planned for 2013 when a fully integrated phase 1 system will be available.

- HERMIT, HLRS, Germany [https://wickie.hlrs.de/platforms/index.php/Cray_XE6]

Tier-1 - HECToR, EPCC, UK HECToR (High-End Computing Terascale Resource) is the UK's front-line national supercomputing service, which is provided by the HECToR Partners including EPCC. The HECToR service consists of a Cray XE6 supercomputer (phase 3) with a peak performance of greater than 800 TFlops, a high-performance parallel file system (esFS), a GPU testbed machine and an archive facility.

- HECToR, EPCC, UK [<http://www.hector.ac.uk>]

Tier-1 - Lindgren, KTH, Sweden Lindgren is a Cray XE6 system, based on the AMD Opteron 12-core "Magny-Cours" (2.1 GHz) processors and the Cray Gemini interconnect technology. It is located at PDC Center for High Performance Computing. It has 16 racks with a theoretical peak performance of 305 TeraFlop. Lindgren is ranked in place 31 amongst the 500 most powerful computer systems in the world (Top500, June 2011). Lindgren is named after the Swedish 20th Century children's book author Astrid Lindgren.

- Lindgren, KTH, Sweden [<http://www.pdc.kth.se/resources/computers/lindgren>]

This guide may also be useful for users of the Cray XT systems which are hosted by PRACE partner sites:

- Tier-1 - Louhi, CSC, Finland [http://www.csc.fi/english/research/Computing_services/computing/servers/louhi]
- Tier-1 - Rosa, CSCS, Switzerland [http://user.cscs.ch/hardware/rosa_cray_xt5/index.html]

1.2 Useful Links

You may find the following resources useful:

- CrayDoc - Documentation for Cray systems [<http://docs.cray.com/>]
- MPI tutorial and reference [<https://computing.llnl.gov/tutorials/mpi/>]
- OpenMP tutorial and reference [<https://computing.llnl.gov/tutorials/openMP/>]

2. System Architecture and Configuration

This section provides an overview of the Cray XE architecture and configurations. Cray XE systems generally consist of two types of nodes: service nodes and compute nodes. Service nodes are used for a variety of tasks on the system including acting as login nodes.

2.1 Processor architecture / MCM architecture

2.1.1 Compute node hardware

Cray XE compute nodes contain two AMD Opteron processors. Depending on the site these can be either 12-core Magny-Cours or 16-core Interlagos processors. These individual processors are connected to each other by HyperTransport links.

Each Opteron processor consists of two NUMA regions (containing either 6 or 8 cores).

On Compute Nodes	HERMIT	HECToR	Lindgren
Processor	Interlagos	Interlagos	Magny-Cours

On Compute Nodes	HERMIT	HECToR	Lindgren
Processors per node	2	2	2
Cores per processor	16	16	12
Clock rate	2.3 GHz	2.3 GHz	2.1 GHz
L1 Cache	16 KB	16 KB	64 KB
L2 Cache	2 MB	2 MB	512 KB
L3 Cache	6 MB	6 MB	5 MB

2.1.2 Vector-type instructions

One of the keys to getting good performance out of the Opteron architecture is writing your code in such a way that the compiler can make use of the vector-type, floating point operations available on the processor. There are a number of different vector-type operations available that all execute in a similar manner: SSE (Streaming SIMD Extensions) Instructions; AVX (Advanced Vector eXtensions) Instructions and FMA4 (Fused Multiply-Add with 4 operands) Instructions. AVX and FMA4 instructions are only available on the Bulldozer architecture.

These instructions can use the floating-point unit (FPU) to operate on multiple floating point numbers simultaneously as long as the numbers are contiguous in memory. SSE instructions contain a number of different operations (for example: arithmetic, comparison, type conversion) that operate on two operands in 128-bit registers. AVX instructions expand SSE to allow operations to operate on three operands and on a data path expanded from 128- to 256-bits - this is especially important in the Bulldozer architecture as a core can have exclusive access to a 256-bit floating point pipeline. The FMA4 instructions are a further expansion to SSE instructions that allow a fused multiply-add operation on 4 operands - these have the potential to greatly increase performance for simulation codes. Both the AVX and FMA4 instruction sets are relatively new innovations and it may take some time before they are effectively supported by compilers.

2.1.3 Bulldozer (Interlagos) Architecture

Each Interlagos processor consists of two NUMA regions (or dies) each containing 8 cores. Each NUMA region is made up of 4 *modules* each of which has two cores and which also contains a shared floating point execution unit. See Figure 2.1 for an overview of the Bulldozer architecture.

The shared FPU in a module is the major difference from previous versions of the Opteron processor. This unit consists of two 128-bit pipelines can be combined into a 256-bit pipeline. Hence, the module FPU is able to execute either a single 256-bit AVX vector instruction or two 128-bit SSE vector instructions per instruction cycle. The FPU also introduces an additional 256-bit fused multiply/add vector instruction which can improve the performance of these operations on the processor. Each 128-bit pipeline can operate on two double precision floating point numbers per clock cycle and the combined 256-bit pipeline can operate on 4 double precision floating point numbers per clock cycle.

Figure 2.1: Overview of an Interlagos processor NUMA region (8 cores). Image courtesy of Wikipedia.

2.1.4 Magny-Cours Architecture

Each Interlagos processor consists of two NUMA regions (or dies) each containing 6 cores.

The FPU in a Magny-Cours processor has a single 128-bit pipeline that can operate on two double precision floating-point numbers per clock cycle.

2.1.5 Service node hardware

The following are the information of the service nodes on each machine. Their service nodes are used for login environment, internal services, etc.

On Service Nodes	HERMIT	HECToR	Lindgren
Processor	AMD Opteron Processor 23	AMD Opteron	AMD Opteron Processor 23
Cores per processor	6	2	6
Clock rate	2.2 GHz	2.6 GHz	2.2 GHz

2.2 Building block architecture

Cray XE compute nodes contain two AMD Opteron processors. Depending on the site these can be either 12-core Magny-Cours or 16-core Interlagos processors. These individual processors are connected to each other by HyperTransport links.

Each Opteron processor consists of two NUMA regions (or dies) each containing either 6 or 8 cores.

The HyperTransport network is also linked directly to the Gemini router chips to provide access to the Cray High-Performance Network.

The layout of a Cray XE compute node is shown in Figure 2.2.

Figure 2.2: Overview of a "Magny-Cours" Cray XE compute node. Image courtesy of Cray Inc.

The number of nodes varies from system to system. The table below summarises the number of nodes on each system.

System	HERMIT	HECToR	Lindgren
Cabinets	38	30	16
No. of Compute Nodes	3552	2816	1516
No. of Cores/Node	32	32	24
No. of Cores	> 113,000	90,112	36,384
Peak Performance	?	> 800 Tflops	305.6 Tflops
No. of Service Nodes	96	24	24

2.3 Memory architecture

All the processors on the the node share 32 GB of DDR3 memory (HERMIT also offers some nodes with 64GB memory). The total memory on HECToR is 58TB and on Lindgren the total memory is 47.38 TB.

2.3.1 Bulldozer (Interlagos) architecture

All 4 modules (8 cores) within a NUMA region (or die) share an 8MB L3 cache (6MB data) with each module having a 2MB L2 data cache shared between the two cores. Each core has its own 16 KB data cache.

The memory bandwidth for each of the PRACE systems is shown in the table below.

System	HERMIT	HECToR	Lindgren
Memory frequency (MHz)	1600	1333	1333
Memory bandwidth per node (MB/s)	102.4	85.3	85.3
Memory bandwidth per socket (MB/s)	51.2	42.7	42.7
Memory bandwidth per module (MB/s)	6.4	5.3	-
Memory bandwidth per core (MB/s)	3.2	2.7	3.6

The main memory bandwidth is 51.2GB/s (6.4GB/s per module, 3.2GB/s per core).

2.3.2 Magny-Cours architecture

All 6 cores within a NUMA region (or die) share an 6MB L3 cache (5MB data) with each core having a 512KB L2 data cache and 64KB L1 data cache.

The main memory bandwidth is 42.6GB/s (3.55GB/s per core).

2.4 Interconnect

Cray XE systems use the Cray Gemini interconnect which links all the compute nodes in a 3D torus. Every two XE compute nodes share a Gemini router which is connected to the processors and main memory via their HyperTransport links.

There are 10 links from each Gemini router on to the high-performance network (HPN); the peak bi-directional bandwidth of each link is 8 GB/s and the latency is around 1-1.5 microseconds.

Further details can be found at the following links:

- The Gemini interconnect [http://docs.cray.com/cgi-bin/craydoc.cgi?mode=Show;q=geminiinterconnect;f=/books/S-2496-3102/html-S-2496-3102//cnl_apps.html#section-4uyokcn1-craigf]
- Workload Management and Application Placement for the CLE [<http://docs.cray.com/books/S-2496-4001/S-2496-4001.pdf>]
- The HECToR's Gemini interconnect [<http://www.hector.ac.uk/cse/documentation/Phase2b/#arch>]
- The topology of the Lindgren network [<http://docs.cray.com/books/S-2496-4001/S-2496-4001.pdf>]

2.5 I/O subsystem architecture

The I/O subsystems are system dependent.

- HERMIT

HERMIT uses the Cray Data Virtualization Service (DVS) which is an I/O forwarding service that can parallelize the I/O transactions of an underlying POSIX-compliant file system.

- HECToR

HECToR phase 2b has 12 I/O nodes to provide the connection between the machine and the data storage. Each I/O node is fully integrated into the toroidal communication network of the machine via their own Gemini chips. They are connected to the high-performance esFS external data storage via Infiniband fibre.

- Lindgren

The primary storage for users of Lindgren is the site-wide Lustre file-system Klemming to which it is connected via Lustre router nodes (currently two). These transport Lustre traffic between the compute nodes on the Cray-internal Gemini interconnect and the Lustre servers residing on PDCs high-performance storage Infiniband-fabric. The current aggregate bandwidth of Klemming is about 5Gbyte/s reading and writing and the size is roughly 300TB.

2.6 Available file systems

Cray XE systems use two separate file systems: the "home" filesystem and the "work" filesystem.

The "home" filesystem is backed up and can be used for critical files and small permanent datasets. It cannot be accessed from the compute nodes, so all files required for running a job on the compute nodes must be present in the "work" filesystem. It should also be noted that the "home" filesystem is not designed for the long term storage of large sets of results. For long term storage, an archive facility should be used.

The "work" filesystem is a Lustre distributed parallel file system. It is the only filesystem that can be accessed from the compute nodes. Thus all input data files must be present on the "work" filesystem before running and all output files generated during the execution on compute nodes must be written to the "work" filesystem. There is no separate backup of data on the "work" filesystem.

The table below shows the filesystem architectures/capacities at the sites.

System	HERMIT	HECToR	Lindgren
"home" architecture	BlueArc mercury 55	BlueArc Titan 2200	AFS
"home" capacity	60TB	70TB	
"work" architecture	Lustre	Lustre	Lustre
"work" capacity	2.7PB	1.0PB	0.45PB
Archive capacity		1.02PB	

Please consult the individual site documentation for further information on the file systems.

- Filesystems on HERMIT, HLRS, Germany [https://wickie.hlrs.de/platforms/index.php/CRAY_XE6_access]
- Filesystems on HECToR, EPCC, UK [http://www.hector.ac.uk/support/documentation/user-guide/resource_management.php]
- Filesystems on Lindgren, KTH, Sweden [<http://www.pdc.kth.se/resources/storage/>]

The HECToR site also includes an archiving facility. More information is available at:

- Archiver on HECToR, EPCC, UK [<http://www.hector.ac.uk/support/documentation/guides/archiver>]

2.7 Operating system (CLE)

The operating system on Cray XE is the *Cray Linux Environment (CLE)* which in turn is based on SuSE Linux. CLE consists of two components: CLE and *Compute Node Linux (CNL)*.

The service nodes of a Cray XE system (for example, the frontend nodes) run the a full-featured version of Linux (CLE).

The compute nodes of a Cray XE system run CNL. CNL is a stripped-down version of Linux that has been extensively modified to reduce both the memory footprint of the OS and also the amount of variation in compute node performance due to OS overhead.

2.7.1 Cluster Compatibility Mode (CCM)

If you require full-featured Linux on the compute nodes of an Cray XE system (for example, to run an ISV code) you may be able to employ *Cluster Compatibility Mode (CCM)*. The installation of this feature is generally site dependent. Please contact your site for information.

3. System Access

The majority of users will connect to the systems using an interactive SSH session. The connection and authentication instructions are typically site-dependent so please consult the documentation for the particular site you are connecting to.

- Connecting to HERMIT, HLRS, Germany [https://wickie.hlrs.de/platforms/index.php/CRAY_XE6_access]
- Connecting to HECToR, EPCC, UK [<http://www.hector.ac.uk/support/documentation/user-guide/connecting.php>]
- Connecting to Lindgren, KTH, Sweden [<http://www.pdc.kth.se/resources/computers/lindgren/how-to/quick-start>]

The following are some basic instructions for connecting to each system.

3.1 HERMIT

The only way to access HERMIT frontend/login nodes from outside HWW net is through ssh using the following command:

```
ssh [userID]@xe601.hww.de
```

The frontend node is the single point to access the entire cluster, where the users can set environment, move data, edit and compile programs and create batch scripts, etc. Interactive usage, *e.g.* running programs which may lead to a high load, is NOT allowed on the frontend/login node. The compute nodes for running parallel jobs are only available via the batch system.

3.2 HECToR

To log into HECToR, the users should use the "login.hector.ac.uk" address:

```
ssh [userID]@login.hector.ac.uk
```

Transferring data to and from HECToR can be performed using scp, GridFTP or bbFTP.

3.3 Lindgren

The Lindgren users can access the system via the login node using a proper login software:

```
lindgren.pdc.kth.se
```

Depending on what operating system (Linux, Windows, Mac OS X) users have on their local computer, they will have to find the correct software to install to access the Lindgren system. Kerberos v5 software (from Heimdal or MIT) is needed to get a Kerberos ticket. Alternatively, the users require SSH software that supports GSSAPI with KeyExchange (from modified OpenSSH) or kerberized telnet software (from Heimdal).

4. Programming Environment / Basic Porting

4.1 Modules environment

The Cray XE system uses the *modules* environment to control the programming environment. For more information on using modules see the output of "man module" on the system or:

- module command man page [<http://modules.sourceforge.net/man/module.html>]

Some quick start commands for the *modules* environment usage:

To check which modules are presently loaded, type

```
module list
```

To search all the available modules, type

```
module avail
```

To search for a specific module, type

```
module show [module_name]
```

To load a specific module for usage, type

```
module load [module_name]
```

To unload a specific module, type

```
module unload [module_name]
```

To swap a loaded module with another one, type

```
module swap [first_module_name] [second_module_name]
```

4.2 Compiler wrapper commands

No matter which programming environment you have loaded you access the compilers via the following commands:

- ftn - Fortran compiler

- cc - C compiler
- CC - C++ compiler

using these high-level compiler wrapper commands ensures that you are compiling for the correct processor architecture on the compute nodes and also makes sure that all the correct library versions are accessed.

You **should not** use the native compiler commands (e.g. pgf90, gfortran) on Cray XE systems.

4.3 Available compilers

A number of different compiler suites are available on Cray XE systems. These may include:

- Cray compilers - the "PrgEnv-cray" module
- Portland group compilers - the "PrgEnv-pgi" module
- GNU compilers - the "PrgEnv-gnu" modules
- Intel compilers - the "PrgEnv-intel" modules (note that Intel compilers have no support for the AMD Bulldozer architecture so will produce sub-optimal code).

Site	Available Compiler Suites
HERMIT	Cray (default), GNU, PGI
HECToR	Cray (default), GNU, PGI
Lindgren	Cray, GNU, Intel, PGI

The default programming environment differs from site to site. You can switch compiler suites with the "module swap" command. For example, to switch from the Cray compiler suite to the GNU compiler suite you would use:

```
module swap PrgEnv-cray PrgEnv-gnu
```

You can also switch between different versions of compilers within a compiler suite by using the "module swap" command. For example, to change the version of the GNU compiler you are using:

```
module swap gcc gcc/4.6.1
```

The compiler version modules for the different compiler suites are:

- cce - For the Cray compiler suite
- pgi - For the PGI compiler suite
- gcc - For the GNU compiler suite
- intel - For the Intel compiler suite

4.3.1 Partitioned Global Address Space (PGAS) compiler support

The Cray compiler suite supports both the Co-array Fortran (CAF) and Unified Parallel C (UPC) PGAS language extensions. For more information on enabling these options see the appropriate section on parallel programming below. You can also find out more at:

- The Co-array Fortran entry on Wikipedia [http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Co-array_Fortran]

- Unified Parallel C homepage [<http://upc.gwu.edu/>]

Cray XE systems also support the Chapel PGAS language through the "chapel" compiler. You can use this compiler by adding the "chapel" module:

```
module add chapel
```

You can find more information on the Chapel language on the Chapel web site [<http://chapel.cray.com/>].

4.4 Available (vendor optimised) numerical libraries

The Cray CLE distribution comes with a range of optimised numerical libraries compiled for all the supported compiler suites listed above. The libraries are listed in the table below along with their current module names and a brief description. Generally, if you wish to use a library in your code you should only need to load the module before compilation.

Library	Module	Description
LibSci	xt-libsci	Cray Scientific Library includes BLAS, LAPACK, BLACS and ScaLAPACK
PETSc	petsc	Portable, Extensible Toolkit for Scientific Computation
FFTW	fftw	Fastest Fourier Transform in the West versions 2 and 3
Trilinos	trilinos	
Global Arrays	ga	

Many of these libraries use the Cray autotuning framework to improve the on-node performance. This framework automatically selects the best version of the library routines based on the size and nature of your problem at runtime.

More information on the library contents can be found on the following web:

- Cray Application Developer's Environment User Guide [<http://docs.cray.com/books/S-2396-601/S-2396-601.pdf>]
- PETSc Website [<http://www.mcs.anl.gov/petsc/petsc-as>]
- FFTW Website [<http://www.fftw.org/>]
- Trilinos Website [<http://trilinos.sandia.gov>]
- Global Arrays Website [<http://www.emsl.pnl.gov/docs/global/>]

4.5 Available MPI implementations

Cray XE systems use a version of the MPICH 2 library that has been optimised for the Gemini interconnect. The version of the MPI library is controlled by the "xt-mpich2" module. All users will have the default "xt-mpich2" module loaded when they connect to the system - for best performance we recommend using the default or later versions.

You can get a list of available versions of the "xt-mpich2" module by using the "module avail" command. For example:

```
module avail xt-mpich2
```

Once the `xt-mpich2` module is loaded, compiling using the standard wrapper compiler commands will automatically include and link to the MPI headers and libraries - you do not need to specify any more options on the command line.

4.6 OpenMP

All of the compiler suites available on the Cray XE system support the OpenMP 3 standard.

Note: in the Cray compiler suite OpenMP functionality is turned on by default.

4.6.1 Compiler flags

The compiler flags to include OpenMP for the various compiler suites are:

Compiler	Enable OpenMP	Disable OpenMP
Cray	-h omp	-h noomp
PGI	-mp	-Mnoopenmp
GNU	-fopenmp	by omission of -fopenmp
Intel	-openmp	by omission of -openmp

You may find these links useful:

- OpenMP Website [<http://openmp.org/wp/>]
- GCC 4.6.1 OpenMP Manual [<http://gcc.gnu.org/onlinedocs/gcc-4.6.1/libgomp/>]
- OpenMP tutorial and reference [<https://computing.llnl.gov/tutorials/openMP/>]
- Intel Getting Started with OpenMP [<http://software.intel.com/en-us/articles/getting-started-with-openmp/>]

4.7 SHMEM

To compile code that uses SHMEM you should ensure that the `xt-shmem` module is loaded. Loading this module will ensure that all the correct environment variables are set for linking to the `libsmm` static and dynamic libraries. You can load the module with the command:

```
module load xt-shmem
```

For more information on using SHMEM, see the Cray man pages at:

- SHMEM Man Pages [http://docs.cray.com/cgi-bin/craydoc.cgi?mode=Show;q=;f=man/xe_libsmm/54/cat3/intro_shmem.3.html]

5 Batch system/job command language

To run a job on Cray XE6 machines, you will need to write a submission script and submit your job to the batch system. As the batch system installed is site-specific, you should consult the local documentation for details on the batch system in operation at the site:

- Using Torque/Moab on HERMIT, HLRS, Germany [https://wickie.hlrs.de/platforms/index.php/CRAY_XE6_Using_the_Batch_System]
- Using PBSpro on HECToR, EPCC, UK [<http://www.hector.ac.uk/support/documentation/user-guide/batch.php>]
- Using Torque/Moab on Lindgren, KTH, Sweden [<http://www.pdc.kth.se/resources/computers/lindgren/how-to/run>]

This section will introduce the basics of writing job submission scripts for Cray XE systems and then go on to look at more advanced batch job topics, including:

- how to run multiple, concurrent parallel jobs in a single job submission script;
- how to run multiple, concurrent parallel jobs using job arrays;
- how to run interactive parallel jobs through the batch system;
- how to select compute nodes with particular characteristics for your job;
- how to use Perl or Python to write job submission scripts.

5.1 Basic batch system commands

This is a very short summary of the most important basic job submission commands on a Cray XE system.

To submit your job to the batch system:

```
qsub your_job_script.pbs
```

To check the job status:

```
qstat
```

To check only your job status:

```
qstat -u $USER
```

To remove your job from the job queue. If your job is running, it will stop it running too:

```
qdel [jobID]
```

5.2 Job submission example scripts for parallel jobs using MPI

```
#!/bin/bash --login

# This example is for systems using Interlagos processors.
# On HERMIT and HECToR the maximum core number per node is 32.
# On Lindgren the maximum core number per node is 24.

# The jobname
```

```
#PBS -N your_job_name

# The total number of parallel tasks for your job.
# The example requires 2048 parallel tasks
#PBS -l mppwidth=2048

# Specify how many processes per node.
# On HERMIT and HECToR valid mppnppn values are from 1 to 32.
# On Lindgren valid mppnppn values are from 1 to 24.
#PBS -l mppnppn=32

# Specify the wall clock time required for your job.
#PBS -l walltime=00:20:00

# Specify which budget account that your job will be charged to.
#PBS -A your_budget_account

# Change to the directory that the job was submitted from.
cd $PBS_O_WORKDIR

# Launch the parallel job using aprun.
# Run the executable my_mpi_executable.x using total
# of 2048 parallel tasks, with 32 tasks assigned per node.
aprun -n 2048 -N 32 ./my_mpi_executable.x arg1 arg2
```

5.3 Job submission example scripts for parallel jobs using OpenMP

```
#!/bin/bash --login

# This example is for systems with Interlagos processors.
# On HERMIT and HECToR: maximum thread number per node is 32.
# On Lindgren: maximum thread number per node is 24.

# The jobname
#PBS -N job_name

# The total number of cores required for your job.
#PBS -l mppwidth=32

# Specify how many processes per node.
#PBS -l mppnppn=32

# Specify the wall clock time required for your job.
#PBS -l walltime=00:20:00

# Change to the directory that the job was submitted from
cd $PBS_O_WORKDIR

# Set the number of OpenMP threads per node
export OMP_NUM_THREADS=32

# Launch the OpenMP job to the allocated compute node using aprun
aprun -n 1 -N 1 -d $OMP_NUM_THREADS ./my_openmp_executable.x arg1 arg2
```

5.3 Multiple 'aprun' commands in a single job script

One of the most efficient ways of running multiple simulations in parallel on Cray XE systems is to use a single job submission script to run multiple simulations. This can be achieved by having multiple 'aprun' commands in a single script and requesting enough resources from the batch system to run them in parallel.

The examples in this section all assume you are using the bash shell for your job submission script but the principles are easily adapted to perl, python or tcsh.

This technique is particularly useful if you have many jobs that use a small number of cores that you want to run simultaneously as the job looks to the batch system like a single large job and is thus easier to schedule.

Note: each 'aprun' command must run on a separate compute node as Cray XE machines only allow exclusive node access. This means you cannot use this technique to run multiple instances of a program on a single compute node.

5.3.1 Requesting the correct number of cores

The total number of cores requested for a job of this type is the sum of the number of cores required for all the simulations in the script. For example, if we have 16 simulations which each run using 2048 cores then we would need to ask for 32768 cores (1024 nodes on a 32-core per node system).

5.3.2 Multiple 'aprun' syntax

The differences from specifying a single aprun command to specifying multiple 'aprun' commands in your job submission script is that each of the aprun command must be run in the background (*i.e.* appended with an &) and there must be a 'wait' command after the final aprun command. For example, to run 4 CP2K [<http://cp2k.berlios.de>] simulations which each use 2048 cores (8192 cores in total) and 32 cores per node:

```
cd $basedir/simulation1/
aprun -n 2048 -N 32 cp2k.popt < input1.cp2k > output1.cp2k &
cd $basedir/simulation2/
aprun -n 2048 -N 32 cp2k.popt < input2.cp2k > output2.cp2k &
cd $basedir/simulation3/
aprun -n 2048 -N 32 cp2k.popt < input3.cp2k > output3.cp2k &
cd $basedir/simulation4/
aprun -n 2048 -N 32 cp2k.popt < input4.cp2k > output4.cp2k &

# Wait for all simulations to complete
wait
```

of course, this could have been more consisely achieved using a loop:

```
for i in {1..4}; do
  cd $basedir/simulation${i}/
  aprun -n 2048 -N 32 cp2k < input${i}.cp2k > output${i}.cp2k &
done

# Wait for all simulations to complete
wait
```

5.3.3 Example job submission script

This PBSPro job submission script runs 16, 2048-core CP2K [<http://cp2k.berlios.de>] simulations in parallel with the input in the directories 'simulation1', 'simulation2', etc.:

```
#!/bin/bash --login

# This example is for the systems using Interlagos processors.
# On HERMIT and HECToR the maximum core number per node is 32.
# On Lindgren the maximum core number per node is 24.

# The jobname
#PBS -N your_job_name

# The total number of parallel tasks for your job.
# This is the sum of the number of parallel tasks
```

```
# required by each of the aprun commands you are using.
# In this example we have 16 * 2048 = 32768 tasks
#PBS -l mppwidth=32768

# Specify how many processes per node.
# On HERMIT and HECToR valid mppnppn values are from 1 to 32.
# On Lindgren valid mppnppn values are from 1 to 32.
#PBS -l mppnppn=32

# Specify the wall clock time required for your job.
# In this example we want 6 hours
#PBS -l walltime=6:0:0

# Specify which budget that your job will be charged to.
#PBS -A your_budget_account

# The base directory is the dir that the job was submitted from.
# All simulations are in subdirectories of this directory.
basedir=$PBS_O_WORKDIR

# Loop over simulations, running them in the background
for i in {1..16}; do
    # Change to the directory for this simulation
    cd $basedir/simulation${i}/
    aprun -n 2048 -N 32 cp2k.popt < input${i}.cp2k > output${i}.cp2k &
done

# Wait for all jobs to finish before exiting the
# job submission script
wait
exit 0
```

In this example, it is assumed that all of the input for the simulations has been setup prior to submitting the jobs. Of course, in reality, you may find that it is more useful for the job submission script to programmatically prepare the input for each job before the aprun command.

5.4 Job arrays

Often, you will want to run the same job submission script multiple times in parallel for many different input parameters. Job arrays provide a mechanism for doing this without the need to issue multiple 'qsub' commands and without the penalty of having large numbers of jobs appearing in the queue.

5.4.1 Example job array submission script

Each job instance in the job array is able to access its unique array index through the environment variable \$PBS_ARRAY_INDEX (for PBSPro) or \$PBS_ARRAYID (for Torque).

This can be used to programmatically select which set of input parameters you want to use. One common way to use job arrays is to place the input for each job instance in a separate subdirectory which has a number as part of its name. For example, if you have 10 sets of input in ten subdirectories called job01, job02, ..., job10 then you would be able to use the following script to run a job array that runs each of these jobs (this example is for PBSPro):

```
#!/bin/bash

# This example is for the systems using Interlagos processors.
# On HERMIT and HECToR the maximum core number per node is 32.
# On Lindgren the maximum core number per node is 24.

# The jobname
#PBS -N your_job_name

# The total number of parallel tasks for your job.
# The example requires 2048 parallal tasks
#PBS -l mppwidth=2048
```

```
# Specify how many processes per node.
# On HERMIT and HECToR valid mppnppn values are from 1 to 32.
# On Lindgren valid mppnppn values are from 1 to 32.
#PBS -l mppnppn=32

# Specify the wall clock time required for your job.
#PBS -l walltime=00:20:00

# Specify which budget account that your job will be charged to.
#PBS -A your_budget_account

# Change to the directory that the job was submitted from.
cd $PBS_O_WORKDIR

# Get the subdirectory name for this job instance in the array
# Note that this example is for PBSPro. For the Torque batch system
# you would need to use the $PBS_ARRAYID environment variable instead
jobid=`printf "%02d" $PBS_ARRAY_INDEX`
jobdir="job$jobid"

# Change to the subdirectory for this job instance in the array
cd $jobdir

# Run this job instance in its subdirectory
echo "Running $jobname"
aprun -n 2048 -N 32 ./my_mpi_executable.x arg1 arg2
```

How you submit job arrays differs depending on whether your site uses the PBSPro or Torque batch system.

5.4.2 Submitting job arrays using PBSPro

The '-J' option to the 'qsub' command is used to submit a job array under PBSPro. For example, to submit a job array consisting of 10 instances, numbered from 1 to 10 you would use the command:

```
qsub -J 1-10 array_job_script.pbs
```

You can also specify a stride other than 1 for array jobs. For example, to submit a job array consisting of 5 instances, numbered 2, 4, 6, 8, and 10 you would use the command:

```
qsub -J 2-10:2 array_job_script.pbs
```

5.4.3 Submitting job arrays using Torque

The '-t' option to the 'qsub' command is used to submit a job array under Torque. For example, to submit a job array consisting of 10 instances, numbered from 1 to 10 you would use the command:

```
qsub -t 1-10 array_job_script.pbs
```

5.4.4 Interacting with individual job instances in an array

You can refer to individual job instance in a job array by using their array index. For example, to delete just the job instance with array index 5 from the batch system (assuming your job ID is 1234), you would use:

```
qdel 1234[5]
```

5.5 Interactive jobs

Note that interactive jobs are not available on all Cray XE execution sites.

Interactive jobs on Cray XE systems are useful for debugging or developmental work as they allow you to issue 'aprun' commands directly from the command line. To submit a interactive job reserving 256 cores (on a 32 core-per-node Interlagos system) for 1 hour you would use the following qsub command:

```
qsub -IVl mppwidth=256,walltime=1:0:0 -A budget
```

When you submit this job your terminal will display something like:

```
qsub: waiting for job 492383.sdb to start
```

and once the job runs you will be returned to a standard Linux command line. However, while the job lasts you will be able to run parallel jobs by using the 'aprun' command directly at your command prompt. The maximum number of cores you can use is limited by the value of mppwidth you specified at submission time.

5.6 Selecting nodes with particular attributes

It is possible to select specific nodes for job execution using the batch system. The resource 'mppnodes' allows you specify a list of particular compute nodes for execution. This can be useful in the case that you are working on a heterogeneous system (with different numbers of cores or different amounts of memory on particular compute node).

For example, to submit a 4 node job (128 cores on a 32 core per node system) to the compute nodes numbered 2, 3, 4 and 5 you would add the following line to your job submission script:

```
#PBS -l mppnodes="2-5"
```

or, if your nodes are not sequentially numbered, for example 2, 4, 6, 8, you can use a comma separated list

```
#PBS -l mppnodes="2,4,6,8"
```

5.6.1 Identifying nodes with particular attributes

To make effective use of the ability to select particular compute nodes for execution you need to have a way to get a list of compute nodes with particular attributes in the format needed for the 'mppnodes' resource. The 'cnselect' command is used on Cray XE systems to perform this task.

For example, to return a list of all compute nodes with 32 cores you would use:

```
cnselect numcores.eq.32
```

or to select all compute nodes with more than 32GB of memory:

```
cnselect availmem.gt.32000
```

5.7 Writing job submission scripts in Perl and Python

It can often be useful to be able to use the features of Perl and/or Python to write more complex job submission scripts. The richer programming environment compared to standard shell scripts can make it easier to dynamically generate input for jobs or put complex workflows together.

Please note that the examples provided in this section are so simple that they could easily be written in bash or tcsh but they provide the necessary information needed to be able to use Perl and Python to write your own, more complex, job submission scripts.

You submit Perl and Python job submission scripts using 'qsub' as for standard jobs.

5.7.1 Example Perl job submission script

This example script shows how to run a CP2K [<http://cp2k.berlios.de>] job using Perl. It illustrates the necessary system calls to change directories and load modules within a Perl script but does not contain any program complexity.

```
#!/usr/bin/perl

# This example is for systems using Interlagos processors.
# On HERMIT and HECTOR the maximum core number per node is 32.
# On Lindgren the maximum core number per node is 24.

# The jobname
#PBS -N your_job_name

# The total number of parallel tasks for your job.
# The example requires 2048 parallel tasks
#PBS -l mppwidth=2048

# Specify how many processes per node.
# On HERMIT and HECTOR: mppnppn values are from 1 to 32.
# On Lindgren: mppnppn values are from 1 to 32.
#PBS -l mppnppn=32

# Set the budget to charge the job to.
# The budget name is site-dependent
#PBS -A budget

# Set the number of MPI tasks and MPI tasks per node
my $mpiTasks = 2048;
my $tasksPerNode = 32;

# Set the executable name and input and output files
my $execName = "cp2k.popt";
my $inputName = "input";
my $outputName = "output";
my $runCode = "$execName < $inputName > $outputName";

# Set up the string to run our job
my $aprunString = "aprun -n $mpiTasks -N $tasksPerNode $runCode";

# Set the command to load the cp2k module
# This is more complicated in Perl as we cannot access the
# 'module' command directly so we need to use a set of commands
# to make sure the subshell that runs the aprun process has the
# correct environment setup. This string will be prepended to the
# aprun command
my $moduleString = "source /etc/profile; module load cp2k;";

# Change to the directory the job was submitted from
chdir($ENV{'PBS_O_WORKDIR'});

# Run the job
```

```
# This is a combination of the module loading string and the
# actaul aprun command. Both of these are set above.
system("$moduleString $aprunString");

# Exit the job
exit(0);
```

5.7.2 Example Python job submission script

This example script shows how to run a CP2K [<http://cp2k.berlios.de>] job using Python. It illustrates the necessary system calls to change directories and load modules within a Python script but does not contain any program complexity.

```
#!/usr/bin/python
# This example is for systems using Interlagos processors.
# On HERMIT and HECToR the maximum core number per node is 32.
# On Lindgren the maximum core number per node is 24.

# The jobname
#PBS -N your_job_name

# The total number of parallel tasks for your job.
# The example requires 2048 parallal tasks
#PBS -l mppwidth=2048

# Specify how many processes per node.
# On HERMIT and HECToR valid mppnppn values are from 1 to 32.
# On Lindgren valid mppnppn values are from 1 to 32.
#PBS -l mppnppn=32

# Set the budget to charge the job to.
# The budget name is site-dependent
#PBS -A budget

# Import the Python modules required for system operations
import os
import sys

# Set the number of MPI tasks and MPI tasks per node
mpiTasks = 2048
tasksPerNode = 32

# Set the executable name and input and output files
execName = "cp2k.popt"
inputName = "input"
outputName = "output"
runCode = "{0} < {1} > {2}".format(execName, inputName, outputName)

# Set up the string to run our job
aprunString = \
    "aprun -n {0} -N {1} {2}".format(mpiTasks, tasksPerNode, runCode)

# Set the command to load the cp2k module
# This is more complicated in Python as we cannot access the
# 'module' command directly so we need to use a set of commands
# to make sure the subshell that runs the aprun process has the
# correct environment setup. This string will be prepended to the
# aprun command
moduleString = "source /etc/profile; module load cp2k; "

# Change to the diectory the job was submitted from
os.chdir(os.environ["PBS_O_WORKDIR"])

# Run the job
# This is a combination of the module loading string and the
# actaul aprun command. Both of these are set above.
os.system(moduleString + aprunString)

# Exit the job
```

```
sys.exit(0)
```

6. Performance analysis

6.1 Available Performance Analysis Tools

All Cray XE machines come with the Cray Performance Tools (module "perftools") installed. These tools include:

- Cray Performance Analysis Tool (CrayPAT).
- PAPI hardware counters.
- Apprentice2 performance visualisation suite.

CrayPAT provides the interface to using all these tools.

There are also other tools available on each system. Please refer to the appropriate documentation at each site.

Site	Tools
HERMIT	Cray PerfTools PAPI
HECToR	Cray PerfTools, Scalasca, VampirTrace
Lindgren	Cray PerfTools, Paraver, Extrae

- Tools on HERMIT [<https://fs.hlr.de/projects/craydoc/docs/books/S-2396-50/html-S-2396-50/chapter-o8nktdbi-brbethke.html>]
- Tools on HECToR [<http://www.hector.ac.uk/support/documentation/userguide/tools.php>]
- Tools on Lindgren [<http://www.pdc.kth.se/resources/software/installed-software>]

6.2 Cray Performance Analysis Tool (CrayPAT)

CrayPAT consists of two command line tools which are used to profile your code: 'pat_build' adds *instrumentation* to your code so that when you run the instrumented binary the profiling information is stored on disk; 'pat_report' reads the profiling information on disk and compiles it into human-readable reports.

CrayPAT can perform two types of performance analysis: *sampling* experiments and *tracing* experiments. A sampling experiment probes the code at a predefined interval and produces a report based on these statistics. A tracing experiment explicitly monitors the code performance within named routines. Typically, the overhead associated with a tracing experiment is higher than that associated with a sampling experiment but provides much more detailed information. The key to getting useful data out of a sampling experiment is to run your profiling for a representative length of time.

Detailed documentation on CrayPAT is available from Cray:

- Using Cray Performance Analysis Tools [<http://docs.cray.com/books/S-2376-52/S-2376-52.pdf>]

6.2.1 Instrumenting a code with pat_build

Often the best way to to analyse the performance is to run a sampling experiment and then use the results from this to perform a focussed tracing experiment. In fact, CrayPAT contains the functionality for automating this process - known as Automatic Profiling Analysis (APA).

The example below illustrates how to do this.

6.2.1.1 Example: Profiling the CASTEP Code

Here is a step-by-step example to instrumenting and profiling the performance of a code (CASTEP) using CrayPAT.

The first step is to compile your code with the profiling tools attached. First load the Cray 'perftools' module with:

```
module add perftools
```

Next, compile the CASTEP code in the standard way on the "work" filesystem (which is accessible on the compute nodes). Once you have the CASTEP executable you need to instrument it for a *sampling* experiment. The following command will produce the 'castep+samp' instrumented executable:

```
pat_build -O apa -o castep+samp castep
```

Run your program as you usually would in the batch system at your site. Here is an example job submission script for a 32-core per node (Interlagos) system.

```
#!/bin/bash --login
#PBS -N bench4_il
#PBS -l mppwidth=1024
#PBS -l mppnppn=32
#PBS -l walltime=1:00:00
# Set this to your budget code
#PBS -A budget

# Switch to the directory you submitted the job from
cd $PBS_O_WORKDIR

# Load the perftools module
module add perftools

# Run the sampling experiment
CASTEP_EXEDIR=/work/user/software/CASTEP/bin
aprun -n 1024 -N 32 $CASTEP_EXEDIR/castep+samp input
```

When the job completes successfully the directory you submitted the job from will either contain an *.xf file (if you used a small number of cores) or a directory (for large core counts) with a name something like:

```
castep+samp+25370-14s
```

The actual name is dependent on the name of your instrumented executable and the process ID. In this case we used 1024 cores so we have got a directory.

The next step is to produce a basic performance report and also the input for 'pat_build' to create a tracing experiment. This is done (usually interactively) by using the 'pat_report' command (you must have the 'perftools' module loaded to use the pat_report command). In our example we would type:

```
pat_report -o castep_samp_1024.pat castep+samp+25370-14s
```

this will produce a text report (in castep_samp_1024.pat) listing the various routines in the program and how much time was spent in each one during the run (see below for a discussion on the contents of this file). It also produces a castep+samp+25370-14s.ap2 file and a castep+samp+25370-14s.apa file:

- The *.ap2 file can be used with the Apprentice2 visualisation tool to get an alternative view of the code performance.
- The *.apa file can be used as the input to "pat_build" to produce a tracing experiment focussed on the routines that take most time (as determined in the previous sampling experiment). We illustrate this below.

For information on interpreting the results in the sampling experiment text report, see the section below.

To produce a focussed tracing experiment based on the results from the sampling experiment above we would use the 'pat_build' command with the *.apa file produced above. (Note, there is no need to change directory to the directory containing the original binary to run this command.)

```
pat_build -O castep+samp+25370-14s.apa -o castep+apa
```

This will generate a new instrumented version of the CASTEP executable (castep+apa) in the current working directory. You can then submit a job (as outlined above) making sure that you reference this new executable. This will then run a tracing experiment based on the options in the *.apa file.

Once again, you will find that your job generates a *.xf file (or a directory) which you can analyse using the 'pat_report' command. Please see the section below for information on analysing tracing experiments.

6.2.2 Analysing profile results using pat_report

The 'pat_report' command is able to produce many different profile reports from the profile data. You can select the type of pre-defined report options with the -O flag to 'pat_report'. A selection of the most generally useful pre-defined report types are:

- ca+src - Show the callers (bottom-up view) leading to the routines that have a high use in the report and include source code line numbers for the calls and time-consuming statements.
- load_balance - Show load-balance statistics for the high-use routines in the program. Parallel processes with minimum, maximum and median times for routines will be displayed. Only available with tracing experiments.
- mpi_callers - Show MPI message statistics. Only available with tracing experiments

Multiple options can be specified to the -O flag if they are separated by commas. For example:

```
pat_report -O ca+src,load_balance -o castep_furtherinfo_1024.pat castep+samp+25370-14s
```

You can also define your own custom reports using the -b and -d flags to 'pat_report'. Details on how to do this can be found in the 'pat_report' documentation and man pages. The output from the pre-defined report types (described above) show the settings of the -b and -d flags that were used to generate the report. You can use these examples as the basis for your own custom reports.

Below, we show examples of the output from sampling and tracing experiments for the pure MPI version of CASTEP. A report from your own code will differ in the routines and times shown. Also, if your code uses OpenMP threads, SHMEM, or CAF/UPC then you will also see different output.

6.2.2.1 Example: results from a sampling experiment on CASTEP

In a sampling experiment, the main summary table produced by 'pat_report' will look something like (of course, your code will contain different functions and subroutines):

```
Table 1: Profile by Function
```

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- Cray XE (V3.1)

Samp%	Samp	Imb. Samp	Imb. Samp%	Group Function PE=HIDE
100.0%	6954.6	--	--	Total

46.0%	3199.8	--	--	MPI

12.9%	897.0	302.0	25.6%	mpi_bcast
12.9%	896.4	78.6	8.2%	mpi_alltoallv
8.7%	604.2	139.8	19.1%	MPI_ALLREDUCE
5.4%	378.6	1221.4	77.5%	MPI_SCATTER
4.9%	341.6	320.4	49.2%	MPI_BARRIER
1.1%	75.8	136.2	65.2%	mpi_gather
=====				
38.8%	2697.9	--	--	USER

9.4%	652.1	171.9	21.2%	comms_transpose_exchange.3720
6.0%	415.2	41.8	9.3%	zgemm_kernel_n
3.4%	237.6	29.4	11.2%	zgemm_kernel_l
3.1%	215.6	24.4	10.3%	zgemm_otcopy
1.7%	119.8	20.2	14.6%	zgemm_onc copy
1.3%	92.3	11.7	11.4%	zdotu_k
=====				
15.2%	1057.0	--	--	ETC

2.0%	140.5	32.5	19.1%	__ion_MOD_ion_q_recip_interpolation
2.0%	139.8	744.2	85.5%	__remainder_piby2
1.1%	78.3	32.7	29.9%	__ion_MOD_ion_apply_and_add_ylm
1.1%	73.5	35.5	33.1%	__trace_MOD_trace_entry
=====				

You can see that CrayPAT splits the results from a sampling experiment into three sections:

- MPI - Samples accumulated in message passing routines
- USER - Samples accumulated in user routines. These are usually the functions and subroutines that are part of your program.
- ETC - Samples accumulated in library routines.

The first two columns indicate the % and number of samples (mean of samples computed across all parallel tasks) and indicate the functions in the program where the sampling experiment spent the most time. Columns 3 and 4 give an indication of the differences between the minimum number of samples and maximum number of samples found across different parallel tasks. This, in turn, gives an indication of where the load-imbalance in the program is found. Of course, it may be that load imbalance is found in routines where insignificant amounts of time are spent. In this case, the load-imbalance may not actually be significant (for example, the large imbalance time seen in 'mpi_gather' in the example above).

In the example above - the largest amounts of time seem to be spent in the MPI routines: mpi_bcast, mpi_alltoallv and MPI_ALLREDUCE and in the program routines: comms_transpose_exchange and the BLAS routine 'zgemm'.

To narrow down where these time consuming calls are in the program we can use the 'ca+src' report option to 'pat_report' to get a view of the split of samples between the different calls to the time consuming routines in the program.

```
pat_report -o ca+src -o castep_calls_1024.pat castep+samp+25370-14s
```

An extract from the the report produced by the above command looks like

Table 1: Profile by Function and Callers, with Line Numbers

```

Samp% | Samp | Group
      |      | Function
      |      | Caller
      |      | PE=HIDE

100.0% | 6954.6 | Total
-----
--snip--
 38.8% | 2697.9 | USER
-----
  9.4% | 652.1 | comms_transpose_exchange.3720
-----
 3.7% | 254.4 | __comms_MOD_comms_transpose_n:comms.mpi.F90:line.17965
 3.1% | 215.0 | __basis_MOD_basis_real_recip_reduced_one:basis.F90:line.4104
 3.0% | 211.4 | __electronic_MOD_electronic_minimisation:electronic.F90:line.1957
 3.0% | 205.6 | __geometry_MOD_geom_get_forces:geometry.F90:line.6299
 2.8% | 195.2 | __geometry_MOD_geom_bfgs:geometry.F90:line.2199
      |      | MAIN__:castep.f90:line.1013
      |      | main:castep.f90:line.623
--snip--

```

This indicates that (in the USER routines) the part of the 'comms_transpose_exchange' routine in which the program is spending most time is around line 3720 (in many cases the time-consuming line will be the start of a loop). Furthermore, we can see that approximately one third of the samples in the routine (3.7%) are originating from the call to 'comms_transpose_exchange' in the stack shown. Here, it looks like they are part of the geometry optimisation section of CASTEP. The remaining two-thirds of the time will be indicated further down in the report.

In the original report (castep_samp_1024.pat) we also set a table reporting on the wall clock time of the program. The table reports the minimum, maximum and median values of wall clock time from the full set of parallel tasks. The table also lists the maximum memory usage of each of the parallel tasks:

Table 3: Wall Clock Time, Memory High Water Mark

Process Time	Process HiMem (MBytes)	PE=[mmm]
124.409675	100.761	Total
126.922418	101.637	pe.39
124.329474	102.336	pe.2
122.241495	101.355	pe.4

If you see a very large difference in the minimum and maximum walltime for different parallel tasks it indicates that there is a large amount of load-imbalance in your code and it should be investigated more thoroughly.

6.2.2.2 Example: results from a tracing experiment on CASTEP

The main summary table from a tracing experiment look very similar to the main summary table from the sampling experiment with the sample counter columns replaced by time columns:

Table 1: Profile by Function Group and Function

Best Practice Guide
- Cray XE (V3.1)

Time%	Time	Imb. Time	Imb. Time%	Calls	Group Function PE=HIDE
100.0%	219.421582	--	--	5661054.0	Total

48.3%	106.010194	--	--	210415.6	MPI_SYNC

22.1%	48.462454	48.436312	99.9%	1700.1	mpi_gather_(sync)
12.0%	26.327995	25.902518	98.4%	13549.0	mpi_bcast_(sync)
7.0%	15.312987	12.925545	84.4%	9.0	mpi_barrier_(sync)
3.3%	7.155499	3.679692	51.4%	90020.5	mpi_allreduce_(sync)
2.8%	6.232381	6.227867	99.9%	1104.0	mpi_scatter_(sync)
1.1%	2.518877	0.841358	33.4%	104033.0	mpi_alltoallv_(sync)
=====					
25.1%	55.160228	--	--	2.0	USER

25.1%	55.159796	65.926769	55.3%	1.0	main
=====					
20.9%	45.947098	--	--	210447.6	MPI

15.0%	32.998366	0.835895	2.5%	104033.0	mpi_alltoallv
4.3%	9.431468	0.338688	3.5%	90020.5	MPI_ALLREDUCE
=====					
5.6%	12.304063	1.288770	9.6%	5240188.9	STRING

5.6%	12.304063	1.288770	9.6%	5240188.9	memcpy
=====					

You should note that the single MPI section has now been split into two sections: MPI and MPI_SYNC. The MPI section now contains the time spent by the MPI library in actually doing work while the MPI_SYNC section contains the time spent in MPI routines waiting for the message to complete.

6.2.3 Using hardware counters

CrayPAT also provides hardware counter data. CrayPAT supports both predefined hardware counter events and individual hardware counters. Please refer to the CrayPAT documentations for further details of the hardware counter events: <http://docs.cray.com/>

To use the hardware counters, you need to set the environment variable PAT_RT_HWPC in your job script when running your tracing experiment. For example:

```
export PAT_RT_HWPC=21
```

(on an Interlagos system) will specify the twenty-first of twenty-two predefined sets of hardware counter events to be measured and reported. This set provides information on floating-point operations, and cache performance.

Note that hardware counters are only supported with **tracing** experiments, not on sampling experiments. If you set PAT_RT_HWPC for a sampling experiment the instrumented executable will fail to run.

When you produce a profile report using 'pat_report', hardware counter information will automatically be included in the report if the PAT_RT_HWPC environment variable was set when the experiment was run.

A full list of the predefined sets of counters can be found on the hardware counters man page on your execution site. To access the documentation, use:

```
man hwpc
```

6.2.3.1 Example: Hardware counter results from CASTEP

```
=====
USER
-----
Time%                               25.2%
Time                               55.178458 secs
Imb. Time                           -- secs
Imb. Time%                           --
Calls                               0.036 /sec          2.0 calls
PAPI_L1_DCM                         31.388M/sec        1732264145 misses
PAPI_TLB_DM                          0.244M/sec         13481844 misses
PAPI_RES_STL                         11.189 secs        25734805221 cycles
PAPI_L1_DCA                          823.706M/sec       45459611237 refs
PAPI_FP_OPS                          2031.598M/sec     112122144958 ops
DATA_CACHE_REFILLS_FROM_NORTHBRIDGE  6.508M/sec         359181707 fills
Average Time per Call                 27.589229 secs
CrayPat Overhead : Time                0.0%
User time (approx)                    55.189 secs      126935432457 cycles 100.0% Time
Total time stalled                    11.189 secs      25734805221 cycles
HW FP Ops / User time                 2031.598M/sec    112122144958 ops  11.0%peak(DP)
HW FP Ops / WCT                       2031.598M/sec
Computational intensity                0.88 ops/cycle   2.47 ops/ref
MFLOPS (aggregate)                   130022.30M/sec
TLB utilization                       3371.91 refs/miss 6.586 avg uses
D1 cache hit,miss ratios              96.2% hits       3.8% misses
D1 cache utilization (misses)         26.24 refs/miss  3.280 avg hits
System to D1 refill                   6.508M/sec       359181707 lines
System to D1 bandwidth                397.229MB/sec    22987629227 bytes
=====
```

The hardware counters for a routine can give hints as to what is causing any problems in performance.

6.3 General hints for interpreting profiling results

There are several general tips for using the results from the performance analysis:

- Examine the routines where most of the time is spent to see if they can be optimised in any way - The "ct+src" report option can often be useful here to determine which regions of a function are using the most time.
- Look for load-imbalance in the code - This is indicated by a large difference in computing time between different parallel tasks.
- High values of time spent in MPI usually indicate something wrong in the code - Load-imbalance, a bad communication pattern, or just not scaling to the specified number of tasks.
- High values of cache misses (seen via hardware counters) could mean a bad memory access in an array or loop - Examine the arrays and loops in the problematic function to see if they can be reorganised to access the data in a more cache-friendly way.

The Tuning chapter in this guide has a lot of information on how to optimise both serial and parallel code. Combining profiling information with the optimisation techniques is the best way to improve the performance of your code.

6.3.1 Spotting load-imbalance

By far the largest obstacle to scaling applications out to large numbers of parallel tasks is the presence of *load-imbalance* in the parallel code. Spotting the symptoms of load-imbalance in performance analysis are key to optimising the scaling performance of your code. Typical symptoms include:

For MPI codes large amounts of time spent in MPI_BARRIER or MPI collectives (which include an implicit barrier).

For OpenMP codes large amounts of time in "_omp_barrier" or "_omp_barrierp".

For PGAS codes large amounts of time spent in synchronisation functions.

When running a CrayPAT tracing experiment with "-g mpi" the MPI time will be split into computation and "sync" time. A high "sync" time can indicate problems with load imbalance in an MPI code.

The location of the accumulation of load-imbalance time often gives an indication of where in your program the load-imbalance is occurring.

Please also see the Load-imbalance section in the Tuning chapter.

7. Tuning

This section discusses best practice for improving the performance of your code on Cray XE systems. We begin with a discussion of how to optimise the serial (single-core) compute performance and then discuss how to improve parallel performance.

Please note that these are general guidelines and some/all of the recommendations may not have an impact on your code. We always advise that you analyse the performance of your code using the profiling tools detailed in the Performance analysis section to identify bottlenecks and parallel performance issues (such as load imbalance).

7.1 Optimisation summary

A summary of getting the best performance from your code would be:

1. Select the right (parallel) algorithm for your problem. If you do not do this then no amount of optimisation will give you the best performance.
2. Use the compiler optimisation flags (and use pointers sparingly in your code).
3. Use the optimised numerical libraries supplied by Cray rather than coding yourself.
4. Eliminate any load-imbalance in your code (CrayPAT can help identify load-balance issues). If you have load-imbalance then your code will never scale up to large core counts.

7.2 Serial (single-core) optimisation

7.2.1 Compiler optimisation flags

One of the easiest optimisations to perform is to use the correct compiler flags. This optimisation technique is extremely simple as it does not require you to modify your source code - although alterations to your source code may allow compiler flags to have more beneficial effects. It is often worth taking the time to try a number of optimisation flag combinations to see what effect they have on performance of your code. In addition, many of the compilers will provide information on what optimisations they are performing and, more usefully, what optimisations they are not performing and why. The flags needed to enable this information are indicated below.

Typical optimisations that can be performed by the compiler include:

Loop optimisation	such as vectorisation and unrolling.
Inlining	replacing a call to a function with the actual function source code.
Local logical block optimisations	such as scheduling, algebraic identity removal.
Global optimisations	such as constant propagations, dead store eliminations (still within a single source code file).

Inter-procedural analyses try to optimise across subroutine/function boundary calls (can span multiple source code files).

The compiler-specific documentation and man pages contain more information about which optimisations particular flags will enable/disable.

When using the more aggressive optimisation options it is important to be aware that the resulting output might be affected, for example a loss of precision. Some of the optimisation options allow changing the order of execution and changing how arithmetic computations are performed. When using aggressive optimisations it is important to test your code to ensure that it still produces the correct result.

Many compiler suites allow pragmas or flags to be placed in the source code to give more information on whether or not (or even how) particular sections of code should be optimised. These can be useful, particularly on restricting optimisation for sections of code where the order of execution is critical. For example, the Portland group compiler can vectorize individual loops, perform memory prefetching, and select an optimization level for a code section.

Cray Compiler Suite

The -O1, -O2 and -O3 flags instruct the compiler to attempt various levels of optimisation (with -O1 being the least aggressive and -O3 being the most aggressive). The default is -O2 but most codes should benefit from increasing this to -O3.

To enable information on successful optimisations use the -Omsgs flag and to enable information on failed optimisations add the -Onegmsgs flag.

- Cray Fortran Compiler Documentation [<http://docs.cray.com/books/S-3901-74/S-3901-74.pdf>]
- Cray C and C++ Compiler Documentation [<http://docs.cray.com/books/S-2179-74/S-2179-74.pdf>]

GNU Compiler Suite

The -O1, -O2 and -O3 flags instruct the compiler to attempt various levels of optimisation (with -O1 being the least aggressive and -O3 being the most aggressive).

The option -ftree-vectorizer-verbose=N will generate information about attempted loop vectorisations.

- GCC 4.6.1 Manual [<http://gcc.gnu.org/onlinedocs/gcc-4.6.1/gcc/>]
- GCC 4.6.1 GNU Fortran Manual [<http://gcc.gnu.org/onlinedocs/gcc-4.6.1/gfortran/>]
- GCC 4.6.1 C++ Manual [<http://gcc.gnu.org/onlinedocs/gcc-4.6.1/cpp/>]

PGI Compiler Suite

The most useful set of optimisation flags for most codes will be: -fast -Mipa=fast. Other useful optimisation flags are -O3, -Mphi, -Mpfo, -Minline, -Munroll and -Mvect.

To enable information on successful optimisations use the -Minfo flag and to enable information on failed optimisations add the -Mneginfo flag.

- PGI Suite Documentation [<http://www.pgroup.com/resources/docs.htm>]

Intel Compiler Suite

The most useful high-level flag is -fast which enables an set of common recommended optimisations. The -O1, -O2 and -O3 flags instruct the compiler to attempt various levels of optimisation (with -O1 being the least aggressive and -O3 being the most aggressive).

- Intel Suite Documentation [<http://software.intel.com/en-us/articles/intel-software-technical-documentation/>]

7.2.2 Using Libraries

Another easy way to boost the serial performance for your code is to use the optimised numerical libraries provided on the Cray XE system. More information on the libraries available on the system can be found in the section: Available Numerical Libraries.

7.2.3 Writing Optimal Serial Code

The speed of computation is determined by the efficiency of your algorithm (essentially the number of operations required to complete the calculation) and how well the compiled executable can exploit the Opteron architecture.

When actually writing your code the largest single effect you can have on performance is by selecting the appropriate algorithm for the problems you are studying. The algorithm you choose is dependent on many things but may include such considerations as:

Precision	Do you need to use double precision floating point numbers? If not, single or mixed-precision algorithms can run up to twice as fast as the double precision versions.
Problem size	what are the scaling properties of your algorithm? Would a different approach allow you to treat larger problems more efficiently?
Complexity	Although a particular algorithm may theoretically have the best scaling properties, is it so complex that this benefit is lost during coding?

Often algorithm selection is non-trivial and a good proportion of code benchmarking and profiling is needed to elucidate the best choice.

Once you have selected the best algorithms for your code you should endeavour to write your code in such a way that allows the compiler to exploit the Opteron processor architecture in the most efficient way.

The first rule is that if your code segment can be replaced by an optimised library call then you should do this (see Available Numerical Libraries). If your code segment does not have an equivalent in one of the standard optimised numerical libraries then you should try to use code constructs that will expose instruction-level parallelism or vectorisation (also known as SSE/AVX instructions) to the compiler while avoiding simple optimisations that the compiler can perform easily. For floating-point intensive kernels the following general advice applies:

- Avoid the use of pointers - these limit the optimisation that the compiler can perform.
- Avoid using function calls, branching statements and goto statements wherever possible.
- Only loops of stride 1 are amenable to vectorisation.
- For nested loops, the innermost loop should be the longest and have a stride of 1.
- Loops with a low number of iterations and/or little computation should be unrolled.

7.2.4 Cache Optimisation

Main memory access on systems such as Cray XE machines is usually around two orders of magnitude slower than performing a single floating-point operation. One solution used in the Opteron architecture to mitigate this is to use a hierarchy of smaller, faster memory spaces on the processor known as *caches*. This solution works as there is often a high chance of a particular address from memory being needed again within a short interval or an address from the same vicinity of memory being needed at the same time. This suggests that we could improve the performance of our code if we write it in such a way so that we access the data in memory that allows the cache hierarchy to be used as efficiently as possible.

Cache optimisation can be a very complex subject but we will try to provide a few general principles that can be applied to your codes that should help improve cache efficiency. The CrayPAT tool introduced in the Performance Analysis section can be used to monitor the cache efficiency of your code through the use of hardware counters.

Effectively, in programming for cache efficiency we are seeking to provide additional locality in our code. Here, locality, refers to both *spatial locality* - using data located in blocks of consecutive memory addresses; and *temporal locality* - using the same address multiple times in a short period of time.

- Spatial locality can be improved by looping over data (in the innermost loop of nested loops) using a stride of 1 (or, in Fortran, by using array syntax).
- Temporal locality can be improved by using short loops that do not contain function calls or branching statements.

There are two other ways in which the cache technology can have a detrimental effect on code performance.

Part of the way in which caches are able to achieve high performance is by mapping each memory address on to a set number of cache lines, this is known as *n-way set associativity*. This property of caches can seriously affect the performance of codes where two array variables involved in an operation exist on the same cache line and the cache line must be refilled twice for each instance of the operation. One way to minimise this effect is to avoid using powers of 2 for your array dimensions (as cache lines are always powers of 2) or, if you see this happening in your code, to pad the array with enough zeroes to stop this happening.

The other major effect on users codes comes in the form of so-called *TLB misses*. The TLB in question is the *translation lookaside buffer* and is the mechanism that the cache/memory hierarchy uses to convert application addresses to physical memory addresses. If a mapping is not contained in the TLB then main memory must be accessed for further information resulting in a large performance penalty. TLB misses most often occur in codes as they loop through an array using a large stride.

The specific cache layout is processor model dependent, consult the site-specific documentation for information of the cache layout on the machine you are using.

7.3 Parallel optimisation

Some of the most important advice from the serial optimisation section also applies for parallel optimisation, namely:

- Choose the correct algorithm for your problem.
- Use vendor-provided libraries wherever possible.

When programming in parallel you will also need to select the parallel programming model to use. As the Cray XE system is an MPP machine with distributed memory you have the following options:

- Pure MPI - using just the MPI communications library.
- Pure SHMEM - using just the SHMEM, single-sided communications library.
- Pure PGAS - using one of the *Partitioned Global Address Space (PGAS)* implementations, such as Coarray Fortran (CAF) or Unified Parallel C (UPC).
- Hybrid approach - using a combination of parallel programming models (most often MPI+OpenMP but MPI+CAF and MPI+SHMEM are also used).

The nature of the Cray XE interconnect architecture, it includes hardware support for single-sided communications, mean that SHMEM and PGAS approaches run very efficiently and, if your algorithm is amenable to such an approach, are worth considering as an alternative to the more traditional

pure MPI approach. A caveat here is that if your code makes heavy use of collective communications (for example, all-to-all or allreduce type operations) then you will find that the optimised MPI versions of these routines almost always outperform the equivalents coded using SHMEM or PGAS.

In addition, due to the fact that Cray XE machines are constructed from quite powerful SMP building blocks (*i.e.* individual nodes with up to 32 cores), a hybrid programming approach using OpenMP for parallelism within a node and MPI for communications outwith a node will generally produce code with better scaling properties than a pure MPI approach.

7.3.1 Load-imbalance

None of the parallel optimisation advice here will allow your code to scale to larger numbers of cores if your code has a large amount of *load-imbalance*.

Load-imbalance in parallel algorithms is where different parallel tasks (or threads) have a large amount of difference in computational work to perform. This, in turn, leads to some tasks (or threads) sitting idle at synchronisation points while waiting for other tasks to complete their block of work. Obviously, this can lead to a large amount of inefficiency in the program and can seriously inhibit good scaling behaviour.

Before optimising the parallel performance of your code it is always worth profiling (see the Profiling section) to try and identify the level of load-imbalance in your code, CrayPAT provides excellent tools for this. If you find a large amount of load-imbalance then you should eliminate this as much as possible before proceeding. Note that load-imbalance may only become apparent once you start using the code on higher and higher numbers of cores.

Eliminating load-imbalance can involve changing the algorithm you are using and/or changing the parallel decomposition of your problem. Generally, this issue is very code specific.

7.3.2 MPI Optimisation

The majority of parallel, scientific software still uses the MPI library as the main way to implement parallelism in the code so much effort has been put in by Cray software engineers to optimise the MPI performance on Cray XE systems. You should make use of this by using high-level MPI routines for parallel operations wherever possible. For example, you should almost always use MPI collective calls rather than writing your own versions using lower-level MPI sends and receives.

When writing MPI (or hybrid MPI+X) code you should:

- overlap communication and computation by using non-blocking operations wherever possible;
- pre-post receives before the matching send operation is called to save memory copies and MPI buffer management overheads;
- send few large messages rather than many small messages to minimise latency costs;
- use collective communication routines as little as possible.
- avoid the use of `mpi_sendrecv` as this is an extremely slow operation unless the two MPI tasks involved are perfectly synchronised.

Some useful MPI environment variables that can be used to tune the performance of your application are:

<code>MPICH_ENV_DISPLAY</code>	set to display the current environment settings when a MPI program is executed.
<code>MPICH_FAST_MEMCPY</code>	use an optimised memory copy function in all MPI routines.
<code>MPICH_MAX_SHORT_MSG_SIZE</code>	tune the use of the eager messaging protocol which tries to minimise the use of the MPI system buffer. The default on Cray

XE systems is usually 128000 bytes. Increasing/decreasing this value may improve performance.

MPICH_COLL_OPT_ON	can give better performance for MPI_Allreduce and MPI_Barrier for large numbers of cores.
MPICH_UNEX_BUFFER_SIZE	increases the buffer size for messages that are received before the receive has been posted (default is 60MB). Increasing this may improve performance if you have a large number of such messages. Better to alter the code to pre-post receives if possible though.

Use "man intro_mpi" on the machine to show a full list of available options.

7.3.3 Mapping tasks/threads onto cores

The way in which your parallel tasks/threads are mapped onto the cores of the Cray XE compute nodes can have a large effect on performance. Some options you may want to consider are:

- When underpopulating a compute node with parallel tasks it can often be beneficial to ensure that the parallel tasks are evenly spread across NUMA regions using the -S option to aprun (see below). This has the potential to optimise the memory bandwidth available to each core and to free up the additional cores for use by the multithreaded version of Cray's LibSci library by setting the OMP_NUM_THREADS environment variable to the number of spare cores that are available to each parallel task and using the "-d \$OMP_NUM_THREADS" option to aprun (see below).
- On the AMD Bulldozer architecture (Interlagos processors) if you use half the cores per node you may be able to get additional performance by ensuring that each core has exclusive access to the shared floating point unit. You can do this by specifying the "-d 2" option to aprun (see below).

The *aprun* command which launches parallel jobs onto Cray XE compute nodes has a range of options for specifying how parallel tasks and threads are mapped onto the actual cores on a node. Some of the most important options are:

-n <i>parallel_tasks</i>	Total number of parallel tasks (not including threads). Default is 1.
-N <i>parallel_tasks_per_node</i>	Number of parallel tasks (not including threads) per node. Default is the number of cores in a node.
-d <i>threads_per_parallel_task</i>	Number of threads per parallel task. For OpenMP codes this will usually be equal to \$OMP_NUM_THREADS. Default is 1.
-S <i>parallel_tasks_per_numa</i>	Number of parallel tasks to assign to each NUMA region on the node. There are 4 NUMA regions per XE compute node. Default is number of cores in a NUMA region.

Some examples should help to illustrate the various options. In all the examples we assume we are running on Cray XE compute nodes that have 32 cores per node arranged into 4 NUMA regions of 8 cores each.

Example 1:

Pure MPI job using 1024 MPI tasks (-n option) with 32 tasks per node (-N option):

```
aprun -n 1024 -N 32 my_app.x
```

This is analogous to the behaviour of mpiexec on Linux clusters.

Example 2:

Hybrid MPI/OpenMP job using 512 MPI tasks (-n option) with 8 OpenMP threads per MPI task (-d option), 4096 cores in total. There will be 4 MPI tasks per node (-n option) and the 8 OpenMP threads are placed such that the threads associated with each MPI task are assigned to the same NUMA region (1 MPI task per NUMA region, -S option):

```
aprun -n 512 -N 4 -d 8 -S 1 my_app.x
```

Further information on job placement can be found in the Cray document:

- Workload Management and Application Placement for the CLE [<http://docs.cray.com/books/S-2496-4001/S-2496-4001.pdf>]

or by typing:

```
man aprun
```

when logged on to any of the Cray XE systems.

7.4 Advanced OpenMP usage

On Cray XE systems, when using the GNU compiler suite, the location of the thread that initialises the data can determine the location of the data. This means that if you allocate your data in the serial portion of the code then the location of the data will be on the NUMA region associated with thread 0. This behaviour can have implications for performance in the parallel regions of the code if a thread from a different NUMA region then tries to access that data. If you are using the Cray or PGI compiler suites then there is no guarantee of where shared data will be located if your OpenMP code spans multiple NUMA regions. We always recommend that OpenMP code does **not** span multiple NUMA regions on Cray XE systems. See below for recommended task/thread configurations.

You can overcome this limitation, when using the GNU compiler suite, by initialising your data in parallel (within a parallel region) or, for any compiler suite, by not using OpenMP parallel regions that span multiple NUMA regions on a node.

In general, it has been found that it is very difficult to gain any parallel performance when using OpenMP parallel regions that span multiple NUMA regions on a Cray XE compute node. For this reason, you will generally find that it is best to use one of the following task/thread layouts if your code contains OpenMP.

MPI Tasks per NUMA Region	Threads per MPI task	aprun syntax
1	8	aprun -n ... -N 4 -S 1 -d 8 ...
2	4	aprun -n ... -N 8 -S 2 -d 4 ...
4	2	aprun -n ... -N 16 -S 4 -d 2 ...

MPI Tasks per NUMA Region	Threads per MPI task	aprun syntax
1	6	aprun -n ... -N 4 -S 1 -d 6 ...
2	3	aprun -n ... -N 8 -S 2 -d 3 ...
3	2	aprun -n ... -N 12 -S 3 -d 2 ...

There is a known issue with OpenMP thread migration when using the GNU programming environment to compile OpenMP code with multiple parallel regions. When a parallel region is finished and a new parallel region begins all of the threads become assigned to core 0 leading to extremely poor performance. To prevent this happening you should supply add the "-cc none" option to aprun.

7.4.1 Environment variables

The following are the most important OpenMP environment variables:

OMP_NUM_THREADS=n	Sets the maximum number of OpenMP threads available to each parallel task.
OMP_NESTED=true	Enable nested OpenMP parallel regions. Note that this functionality is currently only supported by the Cray and GNU compilers.
OMP_SCHEDULE=policy	Determines how iterations of loops are scheduled.
OMP_STACKSIZE=size	Specifies the size of the stack for threads created.
OMP_WAIT_POLICY=policy	Controls the desired behavior of waiting threads.

A more complete list of OpenMP environment variables can be found at:

- OpenMP Environment Variables [<https://computing.llnl.gov/tutorials/openMP/#EnvironmentVariables>]

7.5 Memory optimisation

Although the dynamic memory allocation procedures in modern programming languages offer a large amount of convenience the allocation and deallocation functions are time consuming operations. For this reason they should be avoided in subroutines/functions that are frequently called.

The aprun option `-m size[h|hs]` specifies the per-PE required Resident Set Size (RSS) memory size in megabytes. (K, M, and G suffixes, case insensitive, are supported). If you do not include the `-m` option, the default amount of memory available to each task equals the minimum value of (compute node memory size) / (number of cores) calculated for each compute node.

7.5.1 Memory affinity

Please see the discussion of memory affinity in the OpenMP section

7.5.2 Memory allocation (malloc) tuning

The default is to allow remote-NUMA-node memory allocation to all assigned NUMA nodes. Use the aprun option `-ss` to specify strict memory containment per NUMA node.

Linux also provides some environment variables to control how malloc behaves, e.g. `MALLOC_TRIM_THRESHOLD_` that is the amount of free space at the top of the heap after a `free()` that needs to exist before malloc will return the memory to the OS. Returning memory to the OS is costly. The default setting of 128 KBytes is much too low for a node with 4 GBytes of memory and one application. Setting it higher might improve performance for some applications.

7.5.3 Using huge pages

Huge pages are virtual memory pages that are larger than the default 4KB page size. They can improve the memory performance for codes that have common access patterns across large datasets. Generally, huge pages are accessed by a user using the *libhugelbfs* library (`-lhugelbfs`) and by setting the `HUGETLB_MORECORE=yes` at runtime. Huge pages can sometimes provide better performance by reducing the number of TLB misses and by enforcing larger sequential physical memory inside each page.

The Cray XE system is set up to have huge pages available by default. The modules *craype-hugepages2m* and *craype-hugepages8m* can be used set the necessary link options and environment variables to enable the usage of 2MB or 8MB huge pages respectively. Also, the AMD Opteron sup-

ports multiple page sizes (128KB, 512KB, 2MB, 8MB, 16MB, 64MB). The default huge page size is 2 Mbytes. You will also need to load the appropriate *craype-hugepages* module at runtime (in your job submission script) for hugepages to work.

If you know the memory requirements of your application in advance you should set the `-m` option to `aprun` when you launch your job to preallocate the appropriate number of huge pages. This improves performance by reducing operating system overhead. The syntax is:

`-m<size>h` request *size* Mbytes per PE (advisory)

`-m<size>hs` request *size* Mbytes per PE (required)

7.6 I/O optimisation

I/O subsystems are system dependent. Please consult the individual site documentation for information on the I/O subsystems.

- Filesystems on HECToR, EPCC, UK [http://www.hector.ac.uk/support/documentation/user-guide/resource_management.php]
- Filesystems on HERMIT, HLRS, Germany [https://wickie.hlrs.de/platforms/index.php/CRAY_XE6_access]
- Filesystems on Lindgren, KTH, Sweden [<http://www.pdc.kth.se/resources/computers/lindgren/how-to/quick-start>]

The HECToR CSE team has published some information on how to optimise the I/O on the HECToR system which includes information that may be generally applicable.

- HECToR I/O Good Practice Guide [<http://www.hector.ac.uk/cse/documentation/IO/>]

8. Debugging

8.1 Available Debuggers

The Cray XE system comes with a number of tools to aid in debugging your program. Some systems may also have third-party debugging tools (such as the TotalView debugger) installed. Please consult the site-specific documentation for information on any installed third-party debugging tools.

Site	Available Debugger
HERMIT	DDT, Cray ATP
HECToR	Cray ATP, RogueWave TotalView, lgdb
Lindgren	RogueWave TotalView

Note that the usefulness and accuracy of the information within any debugger depends on your compilation options. If you have optimisation switched on then you may find that the line numbers listed in the debugging information do not correspond with the statements in your source code file. For debugging code we always recommend that you compile with optimisation switched off and the `-g` flag enabled to provide the most accurate information.

8.2 TotalView

Cray XE TotalView provides source-level debugging of Fortran, C, and C++ code compiled by the Cray, PGI, Intel and GNU compilers. The debugging tool provides both a command line interface and a Motif-based GUI. It supports MPI message queue display and watchpoints. There may be some limitations which are site dependent. Please consult your site for further information.

8.2.1 Example, Debugging an MPI application

The following example shows how to invoke TotalView to debug an MPI code.

- Start an X-server on your local machine (if you need to).
- Login to system using 'ssh -Y' (or 'ssh -X') to enable X-windows forwarding.
- Compile your code with the '-g' option. Your code and executable must be in the "work" directory
- Submit the TotalView job to the batch system and leave the terminal you submitted the job from open. Below is an example for a Interlagos based Cray XE system.

```
#!/bin/sh
#PBS -A your_budget_account
#PBS -l walltime=00:05:00
#PBS -v DISPLAY
#PBS -l mppwidth=64
#PBS -l mppnppn=32

cd $PBS_O_WORKDIR

totalview aprun -a -b -a xt -n 64 -N 32 /work/.../myprog.x
```

- When the job starts, the dialogue in Figure 8.1 will be displayed - click 'OK':

Figure 8.1: Initial TotalView dialogue.

- An empty TotalView debugging window will be displayed (Figure 8.2) - click 'Go' to start the program:

Figure 8.2: Empty TotalView debugging window.

- The 'Halt program' dialogue will be displayed (Figure 8.3) - click 'Yes' to begin debugging

Figure 8.3: Initial Totalview dialogue.

- The TotalView debugging window (Figure 8.4) will be displayed with your source code in the middle frame. The top-left frame shows the current call tree and the top-right frame shows the current values of defined variables.

Figure 8.4: Populated TotalView debugging window.

- To add a breakpoint at a particular subroutine or function select 'Debug -> Breakpoint -> At Location...'. and enter the name of the subroutine or function in the resulting dialogue (Figure 8.5) and click 'OK':

Figure 8.5: Add Breakpoint dialogue.

- Click 'Go' in the Totalview debugging window and the program will run until the named routine is reached (Figure 8.6):

- You can add further breakpoints by scrolling through the source and clicking on the line number to the left of the source code.

8.2.2 Example: Using Totalview to debug a core file

To generate core files you just need your working directory to be in the "work" filesystem, and have the line:

```
ulimit -c unlimited
```

in your batch script. Unfortunately the option to tag core files with the process ID is not enabled so if more then one processor dumps core then the core files will overwrite each other. You can use Cray ATP (see below) to produce a merged set of core files for a program that crashes.

To use the TotalView GUI to debug a core file, follow these steps:

- Start an X Server on your local machine and login to HECToR using the '-Y' (or '-X') option to ssh. Launch TotalView :

```
totalview
```

- Click the down arrow on the field showing Start a new process, and from the drop-down list select "Open a core file". The Program and Core file fields display.
- In the Program field, enter the name of the program you wish to debug. In the Core file field, enter the name of the core file produced by this program. If necessary, use the Browse functions to find and select the files.
- Click the "OK" button. TotalView opens the executable and core files.

Alternately, you can use the command-line interface (CLI) to debug the program by entering the following command:

```
totalviewcli program_name core_file_name
```

8.2.3 TotalView Limitations

The TotalView debugging suite for the Cray XE differs in functionality from the standard TotalView implementation in the following ways:

- The TotalView Visualizer is not included.
- The TotalView HyperHelp browser is not included.
- Debugging multiple threads on compute nodes is not supported.
- Debugging MPI_Spawn(), OpenMP, Cray SHMEM, or PVM programs is not supported.
- Compiled EVAL points and expressions are not supported.
- Type transformations for the PGI C++ compiler standard template library collection classes are not supported.
- Exception handling for the PGI C++ compiler runtime library is not supported.
- Spawning a process onto the compute processors is not supported.
- Machine partitioning schemes, gang scheduling, or batch systems are not supported.

In some cases, TotalView functionality is limited because Compute Node Linux (CNL) does not support the feature in the user program.

8.3 Cray ATP

Cray ATP (Abnormal Termination Processing) is a tool that monitors your application and, in the event of an abnormal termination, it will collate the failure information from all the running processes into files for analysis.

With ATP enabled, in the event of abnormal termination, all of the stacktraces are gathered from the dying processes, analysed and collated into a single file called *atpMergedBT.dot*. In addition the stacktrace from the first process to die (hence the probable cause for the failure) is delivered to stderr.

The *atpMergedBT.dot* file can be viewed using the *stat* command that is accessible by loading the *stat* module.

ATP will also dump a heuristically-selected set of core files which will be named: *core.atp.apid.rank* where 'apid' is the APID of the process and 'rank' is the parallel rank of the process that produced the core file.

8.3.1 ATP Example

To enable ATP you should load the *atp* module in your job submission script with the command:

```
module load atp
```

and set the *ATP_ENABLED* environment variable to enable the ATP functionality:

```
export ATP_ENABLED=1
```

and then run your job using *aprun* as usual. Once your application has terminated abnormally you need to log into the service while exporting the X display back to your local machine (you must have an X server running locally) with:

```
ssh -Y username@site
```

Load the *stat* module with:

```
module add stat
```

and view the merged stacktrace with:

```
stat atpMergedBT.dot
```

The stderr from your job should also contain useful information that has been processed by ATP.

8.4 GDB (GNU Debugger)

The standard GNU debugger: GDB is available on Cray XE systems. The debugger currently only supports the command line interface.

There are two components that you must use to debug your parallel program using GDB:

- The 'lgdb' program which launches gdbserver processes on the login nodes.
- The 'gdb' program which connects to the remote program instances (started using 'lgdb') and provides the debugging command line interface.

When you execute your program using 'lgdb' the system will provide instructions on how to connect to the gdbserver process to debug your program. If your site does not support interactive access (i.e. you can only execute jobs parallel jobs in job submission scripts) then you must remember to redirect STDOUT from the gdbserver process to a file you can access while the job is running so that you have access to the information needed to connect gdb to the gdbserver. By default, on many Cray XE systems, the output from STDOUT is only delivered once the job is completed. See the example below for details on this.

8.4.1 Launching your program using 'lgdb'

The 'lgdb' command is used to launch your program and attach a gdbserver process to enable debugging. If you are running interactively, then the syntax for launching a 64 task job and debugging parallel process 0 would be:

```
lgdb --pes=0 --command="aprun -n 64 -N 32 my_parallel_program.x"
```

This command will yield instructions on how to connect the 'gdb' process that will look something like:

```
user@login1:/work/user/debug> less stdout.txt
sending /opt/cray/xt-tools/lgdb/1.4/xt/x86_64-unknown-linux-gnu/bin/lgdbd... completed
sending /opt/cray/xt-tools/lgdb/1.4/xt/x86_64-unknown-linux-gnu/bin/gdbserver... completed

*** create a new window and load the correct lgdb module for each target
*** run gdb from the following path:
/opt/cray/xt-tools/lgdb/1.4/xt/x86_64-unknown-linux-gnu/bin/gdb [PATH-TO-YOUR-APPLICATION]

*** the following gdb target commands should be used in separate windows
*** [Pe=0] to debug this Pe type the following in gdb
target remote nid00003:10000
```

If you do not have access to interactive access and need to run in batch mode then you simply replace the normal aprun command in your job submission script with the call to 'lgdb' and redirect STDOUT to a file. For example:

```
lgdb --pes=0 --command="aprun -n 64 -N 32 my_parallel_program.x" > stdout.txt
```

You **must** redirect STDOUT to a file in this way so you can access the information printed above on how to connect to the gdbserver from the 'gdb' program.

8.4.2 Debugging the remote gdbserver using 'gdb'

Once you have your compute process running with an associated gdbserver using the 'lgdb' command as specified above then you can start the GNU debugger on the command line on the login node with a command such as:

```
user@login1:/work/user/debug> \\  
/opt/cray/xt-tools/lgdb/1.4/xt/x86_64-unknown-linux-gnu/bin/gdb my_parallel_program.x
```

This will give you the '(gdb)' prompt where you can enter the command to link to the gdbserver process to start debugging. For example:

```
(gdb) target remote nid00003:10000
```

Now you can use gdb in the same way as you would if you were debugging a local program.

8.4.3 Useful GDB commands

Please see the documentation for GNU debugger documentation for a full list of the gdb commands. Some of the most often used commands are listed below.

- `break function_name` - (or `b`) insert breakpoint at start of specified function
- `break file:/line_number/` - insert breakpoint at line number in specified file

- continue - (or c) continue running program until next breakpoint is reached
- next - (or n) step to next line of program (will also step into subroutines)
- list - (or l) list source code around current position
- list *start_line*,/*end_line*/ - list source code from *start_line* to *end_line* in current function.
- print *variable_name* - (or p) print the value of the specified variable
- print *array_name*/*(index)* - print value at specified index of 1D array
- print *array_name*/*(index1*,/*index2)*/ - print value at specified index of 2D array
- print *array_name*/*(index)*@/*elements*/ - print *elements* values from the array starting at *index*.
- ptype *variable_name* - print information on the variable type and array dimensions (if this is an array).
- quit - (or q) quit gdb and halt the running program.

8.4.4 Example: debugging an MPI program using GDB

This example illustrates the debugging of the VASP 5 code.

First, you must compile your program with debugging symbols (-g flag). You should also usually ensure that optimisation is turned off (-O0 flag) so that reordering of source code lines does not take place. (Of course, it may sometimes be necessary to include optimisation if this is the cause of the problems.)

In this example we will assume that you are running without interactive access to the compute nodes. Write a job submission script for your job in the usual way but with the following changes: you should load the 'xt-kgdb' module and you replace the standard aprun line with a call to 'kgdb' that contains your aprun command and which redirects STDOUT. For example:

```
#!/bin/bash --login
#PBS -N vasp_debug

# Number of MPI processes
#PBS -l mppwidth=64
#PBS -l mppnppn=32

# Walltime for the debug job
#PBS -l walltime=1:0:0

# Your account code
#PBS -A z01

# Add the Cray GDB module
module add xt-kgdb

# Location of the VASP 5 executable
export VASP_EXEDIR=/work/user/software/VASP/bin

# Change to the directory the job was submitted from
cd $PBS_O_WORKDIR

# Start the gdbserver with our parallel job.
# We make sure we redirect STDOUT (to stdout.txt) so we can access
# the information needed to attach to the remote gdbserver
# We also use the --pes=0 option to start a single gdbserver instance
# attached to the first MPI task
kgdb --pes=0 --command="aprun -n 64 -N 32 $VASP_EXEDIR/vasp" > stdout.txt
```

You should then submit this job in the usual way. Once the job is running, you will be able to inspect the contents of the 'stdout.txt' file to get the ID of the server to attach to using GDB. For example:

```
user@login1:/work/user/debug> less stdout.txt
sending /opt/cray/xt-tools/lgdb/1.4/xt/x86_64-unknown-linux-gnu/bin/lgdbd... completed
sending /opt/cray/xt-tools/lgdb/1.4/xt/x86_64-unknown-linux-gnu/bin/gdbserver... completed

*** create a new window and load the correct lgdb module for each target
*** run gdb from the following path:
/opt/cray/xt-tools/lgdb/1.4/xt/x86_64-unknown-linux-gnu/bin/gdb [PATH-TO-YOUR-APPLICATION]

*** the following gdb target commands should be used in separate windows
*** [Pe=0] to debug this Pe type the following in gdb
target remote nid00003:10000
```

This tells us the 'gdb' binary to use and indicates that we should use GDB to target the remote gdbserver at 'nid00003:10000'. On the login node command line run the specified 'gdb' executable:

```
user@login1:/work/user/debug> \\  
/opt/cray/xt-tools/lgdb/1.4/xt/x86_64-unknown-linux-gnu/bin/gdb $VASP_EXEDIR/vasp

dlopen failed on 'libthread_db.so.1' - /lib64/libthread_db.so.1: undefined symbol: ps_getfpregs
GDB will not be able to debug pthreads.

GNU gdb 6.8
Copyright (C) 2008 Free Software Foundation, Inc.
License GPLv3+: GNU GPL version 3 or later <http://gnu.org/licenses/gpl.html>
This is free software: you are free to change and redistribute it.
There is NO WARRANTY, to the extent permitted by law. Type "show copying"
and "show warranty" for details.
This GDB was configured as "x86_64-unknown-linux-gnu"...
(gdb)
```

and then target the remote gdbserver with the command specified in the 'stdout.txt' file:

```
(gdb) target remote nid00003:10000
Remote debugging using nid00003:10000
[New Thread 22131]
0x0000000012aed60 in __read_nocancel () at ../sysdeps/unix/syscall-template.S:82
82      ../sysdeps/unix/syscall-template.S: No such file or directory.
      in ../sysdeps/unix/syscall-template.S
Current language: auto; currently asm
```

Now we can add a breakpoint at one of our program functions and proceed to it. For example:

```
(gdb) b force_and_stress_
Breakpoint 1 at 0x87f168: file ./force.f, line 1160.
(gdb) c
Continuing.
```

Once the program has reached the specified breakpoint we can start debugging. To see the current backtrace of where we are in the program:

```
Breakpoint 1, force_and_stress_ (kineden=Cannot access memory at address 0x0
) at ./force.f:1160
1160      CALL START_TIMING("G")
Current language: auto; currently fortran
(gdb) bt
#0  force_and_stress_ (kineden=Cannot access memory at address 0x0
) at ./force.f:1160
#1  0x000000000041ad48 in vamp () at ./main.f:2665
```

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```
#2 0x0000000004008e0 in main ()
#3 0x000000001374d14 in __libc_start_main (main=0x4008a0 <main>, argc=1, ubp_av=0x7fffffb548,
    init=0x1375200 <__libc_csu_init>, fini=0x13751c0 <__libc_csu_fini>, rtld_fini=0, stack_end=0x7f
    at libc-start.c:226
#4 0x0000000004007a9 in _start () at ../sysdeps/x86_64/elf/start.S:113
```

We can list the source code lines and add another breakpoint further into the routine by line number:

```
(gdb) l 1160,1180
1160     CALL START_TIMING("G")
1161
1162     DO ISP=1,WDES%NCDIJ
1163     CALL RC_ADD(CHTOT(1,ISP),1.0_q,CHTOT(1,ISP),0.0_q,CHTOTL(1,ISP),GRIDC)
1164     ENDDO
1165     IF (LDO_METAGGA().AND.LMIX_TAU()) THEN
1166     DO ISP=1,WDES%NCDIJ
1167     CALL RC_ADD(KINEDEN%TAU(1,ISP),1.0_q,KINEDEN%TAU(1,ISP),0.0_q,KINEDEN%TAUL(1,ISP)
1168     ENDDO
1169     ENDIF
1170     RHOLM_LAST=RHOLM
1171
1172     IF (INFO%LCHCON .OR. INFO%LCORR) THEN
1173     CALL SET_CHARGE(W, WDES, INFO%LOVERL, &
1174     GRID, GRIDC, GRID_SOFT, GRIDUS, C_TO_US, SOFT_TO_C, &
1175     LATT_CUR, P, SYMM, T_INFO, &
1176     CHDEN, LMDIM, CRHODE, CHTOT, RHOLM, N_MIX_PAW, IRDMAX)
1177
1178     CALL STOP_TIMING("G",IO%IU6,'CHARGE')
1179     ENDIF
1180     !----- FORCES ON IONS -----
(gdb) b ./force.f:1172
Breakpoint 2 at 0x87f37a: file ./force.f, line 1172.
```

and then proceed to this breakpoint:

```
(gdb) c
Continuing.

Breakpoint 2, force_and_stress_ (kineden=Cannot access memory at address 0x0
) at ./force.f:1172
1172     IF (INFO%LCHCON .OR. INFO%LCORR) THEN
```

Now we can examine the values of some of the variables

```
(gdb) ptype info%lchcon
type = logical
(gdb) p info%lchcon
$1 = .FALSE.
(gdb) ptype rholm
type = double precision (0,0)
(gdb) p rholm(1,1)
$2 = 0.051804883959039337
(gdb) p rholm(1,1)@3
$3 = (0.051804883959039337, 0.0083683781999898572, -0.0018751730313048671)
```

The last expression shows the next 3 array element values of rholm starting at (1,1).

Once you have finished debugging you can kill the running program and quit the debugger with the 'quit' command:

```
(gdb) q
The program is running.  Exit anyway? (y or n) y
```